

Sustainable treatment of construction industry wastewater using lime-derived pH regulator and neem leaf-based natural coagulant for its reuse in concreting

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ABSTRACT

Growing water scarcity demands sustainable alternatives to potable water consumption in the construction sector. This study investigates the reuse of construction wastewater for concreting after treatment with natural materials. Lime extract was used as a pH optimizer and neem leaf powder as a natural coagulant. The treated water was analyzed for key physiochemical parameters as per IS standards and evaluated through initial setting time of cement and 28 days compressive strength test of concrete. Results satisfied the requirements of IS 456:2000, confirming that naturally treated wastewater can be safely reused in concrete production & curing.

Keywords : *Construction wastewater, Lime extract, Neem leaf powder, Natural coagulant, plant based pH optimizer, Wastewater reuse*

INTRODUCTION

Water quality directly affects the strength and durability of concrete. Increasing water scarcity highlights the need to reuse treated construction wastewater. Untreated construction effluents contain cement particles, dissolved salts and suspended solids that may affect cement hydration and reinforcement durability. This study employs lime extract for pH control and neem leaf powder for coagulation to improve wastewater quality. The treated water was tested as per IS standards to assess its suitability for concreting applications. The study has evaluated the effectiveness of natural treatment methods and paved way to establish a sustainable, economical and environmentally responsible approach for reusing construction wastewater in concreting works.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Collection of construction wastewater: Concrete mixer wash water

Construction wastewater was collected from the concrete laboratory. The wastewater generated during cleaning of pan mixer and drum mixer after concrete preparation was used for the study. This wastewater primarily contained cement slurry, fine aggregates and suspended solids. The collected wastewater was stored in clean, airtight containers to avoid contamination and used for further treatment and analysis.

Preparation of plant-based pH optimizer: Lime Extract

Fresh limes were procured and thoroughly washed with clean water to remove surface impurities. The limes were then cut into halves and manually squeezed to extract the juice. The extracted liquid was filtered using a clean filter cloth to remove pulp and solid particles. The filtered lime extract was collected in a clean container and used as a natural pH optimizer for the treatment of construction wastewater.

Preparation of Natural Coagulant: Neem Leaf Powder

Fresh neem leaves were collected and washed thoroughly to remove dust and impurities. The leaves were air-dried at room temperature for 24 hours, followed by oven drying at 100°C for 2 hours to remove moisture completely. The dried leaves were then crushed and ground into fine powder. The powder was sieved through a 150µm sieve to obtain uniform particle size. The sieved powder was washed with distilled water to remove soluble impurities and again oven-dried at 100°C for 2 hours. After cooling to room temperature, the prepared neem leaf

powder was stored in an airtight container for use as a natural coagulant in wastewater treatment.

METHODS

Analysis of wastewater

Wastewater was analysed to determine the key physiochemical parameters relevant to reuse suitability in construction applications. pH, acidity, alkalinity, sulphates and chlorides were analysed using a standard field water testing kit following the manufacturer's recommended procedures. Organic and inorganic matter content as well as total suspended solids were determined using laboratory-based gravimetric methods under controlled conditions.

Determination of pH

10ml of sample was taken in a test tube. 4 drops of pH reagent were added. Mouth of the test tube was closed with stopper. Allowed the reagent to get well mixed with sample by gentle up and down rotations. Colour changes occurred. Compared the obtained colour with colour chart provided in the kit & determined the pH value of the wastewater sample.

Determination of Total acidity

10ml of sample was taken in a beaker. 2 drops of acidity indicator were added and swirled. Then started adding acidity reagent drop by drop until the sample turns light pink. Multiplied no. of drops with the factor 25 to get the total acidity value in mg/L as CaCO₃.

Determination of Total alkalinity

10ml of sample was taken in a beaker. 2-3 drops of alkalinity indicator were added and swirled. The blue-green colour was appeared. Started adding alkalinity reagent drop by drop until getting Red-Brown colour. Thus, the total alkalinity in mg/L as CaCO₃ was calculated by multiplying the no. of drops with the factor 25.

Determination of Sulphates

Separated the double tube assembly. Filled the outer tube with 20ml sample. Added 1 level dosing spoon of sulphate reagent to it. Inserted the inner tube and gently moved it up and down for uniform mixing. Sample turned cloudy that represents the presence of sulphate. Reinserted the inner tube gently and watched it from the top until the black spot at the bottom disappears. Noted the graduation mark on the outer tube with respect to the lower edge of the inner tube. Observed value was multiplied with the factor 2 to obtain the sulphate value in mg/L as SO₄.

Determination of Chlorides

5ml of water sample was taken in a beaker. 2-3 drops of chloride indicator were added and swirled. The sample turned yellow. Started adding chloride reagent drop by drop until the sample turns brick red colour. To obtain the chloride content in mg/L as Cl, no. of drops was multiplied by the factor 10.

Determination of organic and inorganic matter

Total solids were determined by evaporating a known volume of sample at 103-105°C to obtain dried residue. The residue was then ignited at 550°C to differentiate volatile solids (organic matter) and fixed solids (inorganic matter). Results were expressed in mg/L.

Determination of Total Suspended Solids

TSS was determined by filtering a known volume of sample through a pre-weighed glass fibre filter, drying it at 103-105°C, cooling in a desiccator and reweighing to constant weight. The increase in filter weight represented suspended solids and was expressed in mg/L.

Analysis of natural pH optimizer and coagulant

Lime extract was used to regulate the highly alkaline wastewater. Gradual addition resulted in stable pH adjustment within the desired range, improving chemical suitability for reuse.

Neem leaf powder acted as a natural coagulant. It promoted floc formation and effective settling of suspended particles, leading to noticeable turbidity reduction.

The combined treatment enhanced wastewater quality in a sustainable and eco-friendly manner.

Determining the optimum dosage of LE and NLP for treatment

Jar test experiments were conducted to determine the optimum dosage of lime extract and neem leaf powder. For each trial, 250ml of wastewater samples was taken in separate jars.

Lime extract was added at concentrations ranging from 0.1% to 0.5%. The samples were mixed uniformly and analysed. Among the tested dosages, 0.4% lime extract produced the near-neutral pH and was therefore selected as the optimum dosage.

Similarly, NLP was tested at concentrations ranging from 0.1% to 0.5%. Improved clarity and better floc formation were observed at 0.4% NLP, which was chosen as the optimum concentration.

Treatment of wastewater

Collected wastewater was stored undisturbed for 24 hours to allow natural sedimentation of heavy particles. The clarified supernatant was carefully separated for further treatment.

The supernatant was treated sequentially with 0.4% of lime extract followed by 0.4% of neem leaf powder. After each addition, rapid mixing was carried out for 2-3 minutes to ensure uniform dispersion, followed by slow mixing for 15-20 minutes to promote floc formation.

The treated sample was then allowed to settle for 24 hours. The clarified water was collected from the top and subjected to further physiochemical analysis.

Analysis of treated wastewater

The treated wastewater samples were analysed for all physiochemical parameters following the same procedures adopted for raw wastewater analysis. Parameters including pH, acidity, alkalinity, sulphates and chlorides were determined using the field water testing kit. While organic matter, inorganic matter and total suspended solids were analysed using standard laboratory gravimetric methods. This ensured consistency and comparability between untreated and treated wastewater samples.

Compatibility check of treated water with cement & concrete

For cement compatibility assessment, 2 cement paste specimens were prepared. One with distilled water and other with treated water. The specimens were examined for consistency and setting characteristics to identify any variation in hydration behaviour.

For concrete compatibility evaluation, 2 sets of concrete cube specimens were cast. The control set was prepared using distilled water, while the experimental set was prepared using treated wastewater. All specimens were cured under identical laboratory conditions and tested for compressive strength at 28 days.

The obtained results were comparatively analysed to determine the suitability of treated wastewater for use in concrete production.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The quality of raw wastewater and treated water was evaluated as per the limits in IS 456:2000.

The untreated wastewater showed a highly alkaline pH of 11, which was reduced to 8 after treatment, falling within the acceptable range of 6-8. Total

alkalinity decreased from 450 mg/L to 225 mg/L, meeting the permissible limit of 250 mg/L, while total acidity remained within the allowable range of 0 ml in raw wastewater and 25 mg/L in treated water as the limit is 50 mg/L.

The treatment process significantly reduced impurities. Organic matter decreased from 300 mg/L to 100 mg/L (limit 200 mg/L), inorganic matter from 9700 mg/L to 900 mg/L (limit 3000 mg/L) and suspended solids from 10,000 mg/L to 1000 mg/L (limit 2000 mg/L). Sulphates (160 mg/L) and Chlorides (150 mg/L) were remained same before and after the treatment and are within the permissible limits as the limit for chloride is 2000 mg/L for PCC and 500 mg/L for RCC and the limit for Sulphate is 400 mg/L.

Cement and concrete performance tests showed satisfactory results with 50% replacement of distilled water by treated water. The initial setting time variation between control and treated water cement moulds was only 5 minutes (205 minutes for control sample, 210 for treated water used sample) which is within the allowable limit of ± 30 minutes. Concrete made with 50% treated water replacement achieved 31.2 MPa, exceeding the 29.3 MPa strength of the control sample and satisfying the requirement of achieving at least 90% strength.

Overall, the results indicate that the treated wastewater is suitable for reuse in concreting applications.

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that construction wash water can be effectively treated using plant-based materials. Lime extract successfully optimized the alkaline Ph, while neem leaf powder acted as an efficient natural coagulant by reducing suspended solids and turbidity.

The treated wastewater showed improved physiochemical properties and was found suitable for reuse in concrete production without adverse effects on performance.

This approach offers a sustainable, eco-friendly and cost-effective solution for construction wastewater management and promotes resource conservation in the construction industry.

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